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Religious Science

How similar are the foundations of the faith of messianic Jews and early Christians?

Abstract

Early Christians and Messianic Jews have the same beliefs because they both follow Jesus as the Messiah and believe in the teachings of the Bible. Both groups believe in the existence of one true God, the divinity of Jesus, the concept of salvation through faith in Jesus, and the importance of living a life guided by the teachings of Jesus and the principles of the Bible. Early Christians, also known as the first Christians or the apostolic Christians, were followers of Jesus who lived in the first century AD. They believed that Jesus was the Son of God and the savior of humanity, as described in the New Testament of the Bible. Messianic Jews, on the other hand, are Jews who believe in Jesus as the Messiah and follow his teachings, while also maintaining their Jewish identity and cultural traditions. Both early Christians and Messianic Jews follow the same Bible, with the Old Testament being revered by both groups as the word of God and the New Testament being accepted by Christians as the fulfillment of the prophecies in the Old Testament. Both groups also share similar practices, such as attending church services, participating in prayer and worship, and observing certain religious holidays and rituals. Overall, early Christians and Messianic Jews have the same beliefs because they both follow Jesus as the Messiah and seek to live their lives according to his teachings and the principles of the Bible.

The first Christians

The first Christians, also known as the early Christians or apostolic Christians, were followers of Jesus who lived in the first century AD. They were a diverse group of people who came from various cultural and social backgrounds, but were united by their belief in Jesus as the Son of God and the savior of humanity. The apostolic Christians believed that Jesus was the long-awaited Messiah (savior) who had been prophesied in the Old Testament of the Bible. They believed that Jesus was divine (God Himself in human form) and had incarnated into flesh to bring salvation to the world through his death and resurrection.¹⁻³ They also believed that Jesus had ascended into heaven and would one day return to earth to establish his kingdom. The early Christians were a minority group in the Roman Empire, where most people followed traditional Roman religions or the newer religion of Mithraism. Despite this, the early Christians were able to spread their message and attract a large following due to the powerful message of hope and salvation that they preached. The early Christians practiced their faith in small communities, known as churches, which were led by bishops and other leaders. They worshipped together, prayed, and studied the Bible. They also practiced baptism, a rite of initiation into the Christian faith, and the Eucharist, a rite in which bread and wine are consecrated and consumed as a symbol of the body and blood of Jesus.^{3,5,6,7,9,10}

Apostolic Christians faced persecution and persecution from the Roman authorities, who saw their message as a threat to the

traditional Roman way of life. Many early Christians were arrested, imprisoned, and even martyred for their faith. Despite this, the early Christians remained steadfast in their beliefs and continued to spread the message of Jesus throughout the Roman Empire and beyond.

Today, the early Christians are revered as the founders of the Christian faith and are remembered for their courage and devotion to Jesus. Their message of hope and salvation continues to inspire and guide millions of believers around the world. The first Christian believers in Jerusalem after the resurrection of Christ were a small group of followers who had been with Jesus during his ministry and witnessed his death and resurrection.^{9,10} These believers included the apostles, who were the closest followers of Jesus, as well as other disciples and believers who had joined Jesus' movement during his ministry. After the resurrection of Jesus, these believers were filled with joy and excitement as they realized that Jesus had indeed risen from the dead, just as he had promised. They were also filled with a sense of mission and purpose, as they believed that they had been chosen by Jesus to spread the message of salvation to the world. The first Christian believers in Jerusalem were a minority group within the city, as most of the residents were Jews who did not believe in Jesus as the Messiah.^{2,4,5,8,9} Despite this, the believers were able to spread their message and attract a following through their powerful witness of Jesus' resurrection and their message of hope and salvation. The believers met regularly in the temple and in private homes to worship, pray, and study the Bible. What is more, they also

practiced baptism, a rite of initiation into the Christian faith, and the Eucharist, a rite in which bread and wine are consecrated and consumed as a symbol of the body and blood of Jesus.^{2,3,5,7,10} The first Christian believers in Jerusalem faced persecution and opposition from the Jewish authorities, who saw their message as a threat to the traditional Jewish way of life. Many believers were arrested, imprisoned, and even martyred for their faith. Despite this, the believers remained steadfast in their beliefs and continued to spread the message of Jesus throughout Jerusalem and beyond. Today, the first Christian believers in Jerusalem are remembered as the pioneers of the Christian faith and are revered as heroes of the faith for their courage and devotion to Jesus. Their message of hope and salvation continues to inspire and guide millions of believers around the world.^{1,6,9}

The Apostolic Christians and the Messianic Jews

The first Christians were in fact Jews because they were followers of Jesus, who was himself a Jew. Jesus was born into a Jewish family in the land of Israel and practiced Judaism, the religion of the Jewish people. He also taught and preached in synagogues, the Jewish houses of worship, and his message was primarily directed towards the Jewish people. The first Christians were Jews who believed that Jesus was the long-awaited Messiah, or savior, who had been prophesied in the Old Testament of the Bible. They believed that Jesus was the Son of God and had been sent

by God to bring salvation to the world through his death and resurrection. They also believed that Jesus had ascended into heaven and would one day return to earth to establish his kingdom. The first Christians were a minority group within Judaism, as most Jews did not believe in Jesus as the Messiah. Despite this, the first Christians were able to attract a following among the Jewish people through their powerful witness of Jesus' resurrection and their message of hope and salvation.^{2,10} The first Christians practiced their faith in small communities, known as churches, which were led by bishops and other leaders. They worshipped together, prayed, and studied the Bible. As mentioned before, they also practiced baptism, a deeply spiritual act. Despite their belief in Jesus as the Messiah, the first Christians did not reject their Jewish identity or traditions. In fact, many of the early Christian believers continued to observe Jewish customs and rituals, such as the observance of the Sabbath and the festivals of Passover and Hanukkah.²⁻⁹ They also continued to study and interpret the Hebrew Scriptures, or Old Testament, in light of their belief in Jesus as the Messiah. It would be an artificial separation to claim that there is any difference between the first Christians in Jerusalem, also known as apostolic Christians, and messianic Jews because both groups have a shared belief in Jesus as the Messiah and follow his teachings.^{8,9} Both groups also have a shared heritage as Jews and a shared belief in the Bible as the word of God. The first Christians in Jerusalem were a group of Jews who believed that Jesus was the long-awaited Messiah, who had been prophesied in the Old Testament of the Bible. They believed that Jesus was the Son of God and had been

sent by God to bring salvation to the world through his death and resurrection. They also believed that Jesus had ascended into heaven and would one day return to earth to establish his kingdom.^{1,2,4,7,8} Messianic Jews, on the other hand, are Jews who believe in Jesus as the Messiah and follow his teachings, while also maintaining their Jewish identity and cultural traditions. Like the first Christians in Jerusalem, messianic Jews believe in the existence of one true God, the divinity of Jesus, the concept of salvation through faith in Jesus, and the importance of living a life guided by the teachings of Jesus and the principles of the Bible. Both the first Christians in Jerusalem and messianic Jews follow the same Bible, with the Old Testament being revered by both groups as the word of God and the New Testament being accepted by Christians as the fulfillment of the prophecies in the Old Testament.^{1,10} Both groups also share similar practices, such as attending church services, participating in prayer and worship, and observing certain religious holidays and rituals. Overall, it would be an artificial separation to claim that there is any difference between the first Christians in Jerusalem and messianic Jews because both groups have a shared belief in Jesus as the Messiah and follow his teachings, while also maintaining their Jewish identity and cultural traditions.^{1-7,9}

Panentheist believes

Basically messianic Jews are panentheists, as panentheism is a belief that God is present in and transcends the universe, while messianic Jews have a variety of beliefs about the nature of God. Messianic

Jews may hold panentheistic beliefs due to their understanding of the Bible and their belief in Jesus as the Messiah. One reason why messianic Jews may be panentheists is because of their belief in the unity and indivisibility of God. The Old Testament of the Bible, which is revered by both messianic Jews and Jews, teaches that God is one and indivisible, and that there is no other god besides him. This belief in the unity and indivisibility of God may lead messianic Jews to view God as present in and transcending the universe, as described in panentheism. Another reason why messianic Jews may be panentheists is because of their belief in the divinity of Jesus. Messianic Jews believe that Jesus is the Messiah, or savior, who was prophesied in the Old Testament and who was sent by God to bring salvation to the world through his death and resurrection. They also believe that Jesus is the Son of God and is divine. This belief in the divinity of Jesus may lead some messianic Jews to view God as present in and transcending the universe, as described in panentheism.^{2,5,7,9,10}

However, not all messianic Jews hold panentheistic beliefs and messianic Judaism is quite diverse with a variety of beliefs about the nature of God. Some messianic Jews may hold traditional Jewish beliefs about the nature of God, while others may hold more modern or eclectic beliefs. The beliefs of individual messianic Jews are influenced by a variety of factors, including their personal experiences, their understanding of the Bible, and their cultural and historical context. The same is true for many of the apostolic Christians.^{4,6,7,8,10} Many of them also believed that God is present in and transcends the universe,

while the first Christians had a variety of beliefs about the nature of God. However, some of the first Christians may have held panentheistic beliefs due to their understanding of the Bible and their belief in Jesus as the Messiah - and above all: trinity.^{1,2,7}

Trinity

Trinity is the belief that God is one being who exists in at least three aspects: the Father, the Son, and the Holy Spirit. This belief is central to Christianity, many Messianic Jews and is affirmed by many Christian denominations and congregations such as Catholicism, Orthodoxy, and Protestantism. From a panentheist perspective, the doctrine of the Trinity can be understood as a way of explaining the unity and indivisibility of God, while also recognizing the distinctiveness and diversity of the three persons of the Trinity. Panentheism is a belief that God is present in and transcends the universe, and the doctrine of the Trinity can be seen as consistent with this belief in that it suggests that God is present and active in the world through the three aspects of the Father, the Son, and the Holy Spirit. The Father is traditionally understood as the creator (‘the architect’, the ‘builder’) and sustainer of the universe, the Son as the incarnate Word of God and the savior of humanity, and the Holy Spirit as the source of divine revelation and the agent of transformation and renewal which creates what we perceive as reality.^{2,6,8} From a panentheist perspective, the three aspects of the Trinity may be seen as different aspects or expressions of the divine

presence and activity in the world, while also being united in the one being of God. It is important to note that the doctrine of the Trinity is a complex and nuanced belief that has been interpreted and understood in various ways throughout Christian history.

Conclusion

It would be a mistake to not regard the first Christians and the messianic Jews as more or less identical in their beliefs because the first Christians were actually messianic Jews. The term "Christian" refers to followers of Jesus Christ, and the first followers of Jesus were Jewish. They believed that Jesus was the Messiah, or savior, promised in Jewish scripture. As such, they retained many of their Jewish beliefs and practices, including their belief in the same God as the Jews and their adherence to Jewish laws and traditions. Furthermore, the early Christians saw themselves as a fulfillment of Jewish prophecy and a continuation of the Jewish faith.^{3,7,9} They preached to other Jews and sought to convince them that Jesus was the long-awaited Messiah. It was only later, after the spread of Christianity to non-Jewish communities, that the term "Christian" came to refer to a distinct religious group separate from Judaism. Therefore, it would be incorrect to view the first Christians as separate from or distinct from the messianic Jews, as they were one and the same group. They shared the same beliefs and practices and saw themselves as a part of the same faith tradition.^{1,8,9}

Conflict of interests

None declared

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